

Interview Questions

Introduction

- Short introduction of the project, researchers, and the interview process
 - Informed consent before recording the interview, highlight the anonymization of the collected data
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PART 1

1. Stakeholders' characteristics

- Gender (without question, researcher marks)
- Stakeholder group (without question, researcher marks)

2. Relationship with the company and community

- What is your personal and professional relationship with the quarrying company and the community?

3. Knowledge of the region

- How good is your knowledge of the region - on a scale of 1 – 10, with 1 being very poor, 10 being very good?

4. Associations

- Name the 5 most important features that characterize the quarries in your region.
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PART 2

5. Power and interest in the region

- Who has had the largest power in the region?
- What is the distribution of interest in the region?

6. Community engagement in quarry planning and rehabilitation

- Is the quarrying company engaging with the community? If so, how often and where?
 - Have you been included in the planning of the rehabilitation of the quarries in your region? If so, can you describe the planning process?
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PART 3

7. Future vision

- What is your future vision of the region and specifically the quarries?
- What are the drivers of the vision? What are the bottlenecks of the vision?

8. Concerns

- What are your concerns about the future of the region and specifically the quarries?
- How these concerns could be overcome?

Final words

- Thanks.
- A brief comment on the next steps and how we will use the data (emphasize anonymity).